

Further record of *Golunda ellioti* Gray, 1837 from South East of Iran with notes on its postcranial skeleton

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The Indian Bush Rat, *Golunda ellioti* Gray, 1837 is the only type species of the monotypic genus *Golunda* Gray, 1837, which is known in family Muridae by its grooved upper incisors. This species has special columnar structure in its upper molars, which bear high separated cusps. The genus is believed to form one of the more primitive ancestors in this family. *Golunda ellioti* is a rat-like rodent and is very similar to *Rattus rattus* but its size is considerably smaller and the tail is slightly shorter than the head and body length. Also the tail is much better covered with short hairs than in *Rattus* species. The head of *G. ellioti* is vole-like in its appearance. Eyes are relatively bigger than *Rattus* species and ear is more flattened, circular and well covered with hairs. Bush rat has stout well-developed feet with four digits on the forefeet and a very short vestigial thumb, bearing a claw. The soles of the hindfeet are always blackish unlike other murids. With their naked soles they are adapted for climbing trees and low bushes. Incisors are reddish and deeply grooved. Due to their strongly cuspidate molars, they are well adapted to feeding on hard seeds (Roberts, 1977). Type locality of this species is India, Dharwar and it is distributed in the SE of Iran (Misonne, 1990), Pakistan (Roberts, 1977), Nepal (Ellerman, 1966), N and NE India south through Indian peninsula to Sri Lanka (Agrawal, 2000).

In this study, we captured two adults as well as one immature specimen from Jiroft (28° 33'17.33"N and 57° 43'46.63"E, 615 m asl) in a Palm and Citrus orchards (Fig. 1).

Absence of suprameatal triangle as well as cheek teeth length are characteristics of this species. The third upper and lower molars are slightly longer than the second one, and there is no posterostyle in first and second upper molars. Detailed Morphometric data and the morphological characteristics of the specimens were presented in table 1 and figure 2 respectively.

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Comparison of postcranial skeleton between *G. ellioti* and *R. norvegicus* showed several differences as follow: resistance to tensile forces in the shoulder region is partly based on the development of the infrapinuous fossa (Argot, 2003). This pattern is less observed in *G. ellioti* than *R. norvegicus*. On the dorsal margin of the ischium, just posterior to the acetabulum, a rugose tuberosity suggests strong pull exerted by the ischio- caudalis (Argot, 2003). This is the characteristic of *G. ellioti* in comparison to *R. norvegicus*. Fossoriality was strongly expressed by greater robusticity in long limb bones of the fore and hind limbs (Weisbecker & Schmid, 2007). It could be seen in *G. ellioti*. Other skeletal differences between *G. ellioti* and *R. norvegicus* are listed in the Appendix.

All current information about the evolutionary history of *Golunda ellioti* confirms its endemism to the Indian subcontinent (Wilson & Reeder, 2005). This species has survived in the extreme southern coastal region of Sindh as well as in the extreme north- eastern part of the Punjab adjacent to the Himalayan foothills, but it is not highly adapted to arid regions (Roberts, 1977). Considering that this species was not found in the west of the Hub river Valley near Karachi until its first record from Jiroft in south of Jabal- Barez mountains (with subtropical climate) (Nazari & Farid, 1991), its presence in Iran near Persian Gulf raises questions about its origin and the way it has penetrated Iran. We need further investigations to clarify these facts.

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TABLE 1. Morphometric characters of *G. ellioti*.

Row	Variable	Mean (mm)
1	Length of upper cheek teeth row from alveole	6.09
2	Length of first upper molar	2.76
3	Width of first upper molar	2.10
4	Length of second upper molar	2.55
5	Width of second upper molar	2.17
6	Length of third upper molar	2.01
7	Width of third upper molar	1.73
8	Length of upper diastema	7.58
9	Length of nasal	8.80
10	Width of Nasal	4.57
11	Length of anterior palatine foramen	4.55
12	Infraorbital thickness	3.44
13	Length of lower cheek teeth row from alveole	6.39
14	Length of first lower molar	2.75
15	Width of first lower molar	1.66
16	Length of second lower molar	1.82
17	Width of second lower molar	1.60
18	Length of third lower molar	1.75
19	Width of third lower molar	1.73
20	Length of lower diastema	4.09
21	Mandibular length	16.77
22	Mandibular height	8.66
23	Head and body length	112.1
24	Tail length	101
25	Hind foot length	23.5

FIGURE 1. A: Sampling locality and B: Habitat of *G. ellioti* in Jiroft, Kerman province, Iran.

Figure 2. A: Skull and mandible of *G. ellioti* from dorsal (1), ventral (2), lateral (3) and medial (4) view and B: Upper (Left) and lower (Right) left cheek teeth row of *G. ellioti* (X20).

Appendix. Postcranial skeleton of *G. ellioti* and *R. norvegicus*: In a general comparison.

Skeletal component	Character	Character state			
		<i>Golunda ellioti</i>		<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	
Total number of thoracic and lumbar vertebra (respectively)		12- 7	-	13- 6	-
Scapula	Width of supraspinous fossa	Smaller			
Humer	Deltoid tuberosity shape	Hooked			
Ulna	Semilunar notch shape	Angulate			
	Presence of small pit above semilunar notch	Present			
Innominate bone	Iliopectinal eminence	Not obvious			
	Shape of dorsal margin of ischium body	Triangular			